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**РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ В РАЗВИТИИ
АУТСОРСИНГОВЫХ УСЛУГ В ТРАНСПОРТНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ
ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНО ВНЕДРЕНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ
УЗБЕКИСТАН.**

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Аннотация. появление цифровых платформ существенно изменило аутсорсинговые услуги в транспортной системе, позволив более эффективно и оптимально управлять ресурсами и операциями. В данной статье рассматривается роль цифровых платформ в развитии аутсорсинговых услуг в транспортной системе, с особым акцентом на внедрение этих платформ в Республике Узбекистан

Ключевые слова: цифровой аутсорсинг, глобальная трансформация, эффективность аутсорсинга, логистические услуги.

**THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
OUTSOURCING SERVICES IN THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM REGARDING
THE IMPLEMENTATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.**

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Abstract. the emergence of digital platforms has significantly changed outsourcing services in the transport system, allowing more efficient and optimal management of resources and operations. This article examines the role of digital platforms in the development of outsourcing services in the transport system, with a special focus on the introduction of these platforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: digital outsourcing, global transformation, outsourcing effectiveness, logistics services.

Introduction. In 2020, the government established a Software and Information Technology Park in Uzbekistan in order to encourage the development of globally competitive software products and the creation of an ICT business outsourcing cluster. The technology park offers business acceleration and incubation services to support the transition of business ideas to commercialization of products and services. The technology park offers business acceleration and incubation services to support the transition of business ideas to commercialization of products and services. In addition to the technopark, Uzbekistan has a developed system of innovative policy mechanisms that support the growth of digital business. For example, C.A.T. Projects like startups. Science Accelerator", "IdeaLab", "Startup Factory" and "WomenTech". The technology park is also home to the Academy of Information Technologies, which offers training in digital technologies. And the most popular of today's main competitive services in the transport system is definitely outsourcing. By contrast, many service companies update and improve their inventory in order to get more profit, and the introduction of digital platforms in outsourcing services has become one of the urgent problems of their improvement. A number of reforms are being implemented in this regard, including in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, as well as these issues, are expressed in the decision on "Measures to improve transport infrastructure and diversify foreign trade routes in 2018-2022".

Significant results were achieved as a result of the implementation of the measures provided for in these documents. In particular, the volume of services provided by the type of economic activity "information and communication" increased by more than one and a half times from 2020 to 2022, from 13.9 trillion sums to 22.9

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trillion. In addition, the share of the digital economy in the GDP of Uzbekistan increased from 1.99 percent to 2.77 percent in 2022 compared to 2020.

Exports of information and communication technology services increased from 169.3 million dollars to 306 million dollars from 2020 to 2022. Exports of computer programming services will grow to \$123 million in 2022 compared to \$15 million in 2020, indicating that the industry's latent potential has been realized. At the moment, the number of IT-park residents is 1122 companies, of which about 30% are exporters¹.

Main part. Outsourcing in the transport system refers to the practice of transferring certain activities related to transport to external service providers. This may include tasks such as fleet management logistics planning data analysis and customer support. The use of digital platforms has become crucial in the development and introduction of outsourcing services in the transport system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These platforms offer a number of advantages and provide solutions to various challenges faced by the transportation industry.

One of the main advantages of using digital platforms in outsourcing services is their ability to simplify operations and increase efficiency. These platforms offer tools to automate real-time shipment tracking processes and optimize routes for maximum cost effectiveness. By using these platforms, transportation companies in Uzbekistan can significantly reduce manual labor and increase overall productivity. Looking at the graph below, we can see how digital transformation is accelerating globally:

¹Bakhtiyor Ismailov, “ *Uzbekistan in the process of digitalization development* ” result in 2022 and prospects for 2023

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Figure-1. Global digital transformation spending 2017-2028²

In addition, digital platforms enable seamless communication and collaboration between various stakeholders in the transportation system. This is particularly useful in the context of outsourcing where there is a need to coordinate activities between the transport company and the outsourcing service provider. With digital platforms, information can be easily shared, updates delivered in real-time and any issues or delays resolved quickly.

Digital platforms also provide access to large amounts of data that can be used for better decision-making and strategic planning. By analyzing data related to transportation operations, companies can identify areas for improvement, optimize resource allocation, and increase overall efficiency. This data-driven approach helps identify cost-effective opportunities to reduce fuel consumption and improve customer satisfaction.

In addition to these advantages, digital platforms offer transparency and visibility. The transport sector in Uzbekistan faces problems such as theft fraud and inefficiency due to lack of control.

However, there are also some disadvantages to consider when using digital platforms for outsourcing services in the transportation system. First, there is the risk of technological dependence. If the digital platform experiences technical problems or malfunctions, it may disrupt operations and cause delays or service interruptions. It is essential for transport companies to have contingency plans in place to mitigate such

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risks. Second, there may be concerns about data privacy and security. The transport industry deals with sensitive data such as customer details, shipment data and financial records. Transport companies must ensure that the digital platforms they use follow strict security protocols and take robust data protection measures. But despite these shortcomings, the role of the improvement of digital platforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan is very large on a global scale. Here are 5 factors for digital outsourcing that have been tested all over the world:

- ✓ Cost-Effectiveness;
- ✓ Time Efficiency;
- ✓ Access To Specialized Skills and Expertise;
- ✓ Increased Focus On Core Business Areas;
- ✓ Improved Scalability.

If we look at the following graph, the share of logistics services in the improvement of digital platforms of outsourcing services in the transport system by types of transport:

Figure-2. The expected logistics market from 2017 to 2027 by types of transport³

Conclusion. The role of digital platforms in the provision of outsourcing services in the transport system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is important. These platforms offer many advantages, such as improved efficiency, collaborative access to data-driven insights, and increased transparency. However, it is critical for transportation companies to mitigate the risks associated with technological dependency and ensure the security and confidentiality of confidential information. Next, there are enterprises

³ www.kbvresearch.com

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that are currently avoiding the active use of digital transformation of transport and logistics, perhaps they should reconsider their position. To reap the many benefits of digitization. However, there is still room for improvement to facilitate digital transformation and make the role of technology in the sector more clear. As a result of the growing competition, the quality and price of products have become equal, and the speed of delivery is now a decisive factor for customers and clients. By using digital platforms, Uzbekistan can take advantage of outsourcing to ensure growth and development in the transportation industry. New digital information technologies are forcing more and more companies to use technologies such as these factors to improve efficiency and reduce production and service costs. Demand and innovation such as new ways to enter the market and technologies attract new customers. This gives businesses an additional competitive advantage.

In particular, intermodal and multimodal transport and logistics systems achieve a high service life, which provides an opportunity to quickly adapt to new market characteristics. Thus, if the way to improve transport and logistics digital platforms is opened, if the government and transport companies work in harmony, it will provide an opportunity to improve the transport potential of the Republic not only in Central Asia, but also to increase interregional market transport relations.

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